

Amusing the Spirits through the Music: *Coul Ruup* Rituals in Cambodia

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Abstract

This paper examines the interactive communication between musicians, spirit and medium in rituals of possession and healing, *coul ruup*, which are still performed in various Cambodian rural areas including Siem Reap and Kampong Spøi provinces respectively in the northwest and southeast areas of the country, where I conducted my doctoral research. Through a performance-oriented analysis of the structure of *coul ruup* ritual and musical features of the *phleng arak* music within the ritual context, this paper aims to show the role of *phleng arak* music in structuring the ceremony and amusing the spirits. As a result, ethnographic excerpts from the ceremony are juxtaposed with more general commentary giving additional interpretive and contextual information. This paper provides a first classification and analysis of the *phleng arak* repertoire focusing on the features strictly connected to the possession stage and the nature of the *arak* spirits and contributes to broad the knowledge on Khmer rituals of possession which deserve more scholarly attention.

Divertire gli Spiriti attraverso la musica: i rituali *coul ruup* in Cambogia. *Questo saggio mette in luce la comunicazione interattiva tra musicisti, spiriti e medium nei rituali di possessione e guarigione, coul ruup, che sono ancora eseguiti in varie aree rurali della Cambogia comprese le province di Siem Reap e Kampong Spøi rispettivamente nelle aree nord-ovest e sud-est del paese, dove ho condotto la mia ricerca di dottorato. Attraverso un'analisi della struttura del culto di possessione coul ruup e delle caratteristiche della musica phleng arak all'interno del contesto rituale, questo articolo mira a dimostrare il ruolo della musica phleng arak nello scandire le diverse fasi della possessione e nel divertire gli spiriti. Di conseguenza, estratti etnografici della cerimonia sono giustapposti a commenti più generali fornendo ulteriori informazioni interpretative e contestuali relativi a diversi aspetti della cerimonia coul ruup. Questo saggio fornisce una prima classificazione e analisi del repertorio phleng arak e contribuisce ad ampliare la conoscenza dei rituali di possessione khmer che meritano maggiore attenzione da parte degli studiosi.*

1. Introduction

Coul ruup or *coul arak*¹ (entering the medium or the *arak* spirit) are rituals of possession and healing which are still performed in various Cambodian rural areas including Siem Reap and Kampong Spøi provinces respectively in the northwest and southeast areas of the country, where I conducted my doctoral research. In the *coul ruup* ceremony, one or more *arak* spirits possess a *ruup* (medium) who is an intermediary between the spirits and the human spheres.

Mediums and musicians describe the *arak* as lively and nasty spirits; they enjoy eating, dancing, having fun and above all listening to the music. They are considered to be benevolent and, at the same time, malevolent spirits. In fact, on the one hand, they protect their followers; on the other they can harm them. Consequently, it is necessary to perform rituals of exorcism and therapy called *coul ruup* or *coul arak*. In this context, a specific repertoire called *phleng arak* (music for *arak* spirits) has the function to evoke the *arak* spirits and to please them so that they leave the body of the sick person.

However, music is not only a means of their identification and manifestation, but it also has the function of amusing the spirits. In fact, the spirits can even request songs from other genres, if they like. In other Asian possession rituals, musicians play songs from different repertoires which are also part of the fixed structure of the ceremony in order to entertain the medium and the audience (Chiarofonte 2014, Mills 2003, Norton 2000, Shahriari 2006), while in *coul ruup* ceremony, the only protagonist is the medium who reflects the *arak*'s enjoyment and excitement in listening to the music. The human audience is not involved in the interactive communication between spirits, medium and musicians but just observes the development of the ritual.

To understand the role of *phleng arak* music within its ritual context and the power of *arak* spirits in the Khmers' life, I discuss the co-existence of modern and traditional medical treatments to give an insight into the reasons why the beliefs in *arak* spirits are still alive among rural people. Successively, I briefly introduce the nature of the *arak* spirits from the musicians' and mediums' perspective, the general structure of the *coul ruup* ceremony including the participants and their role, and the multipurpose of the ritual. The second part of the paper narrows down to the *phleng arak* musical features that amuse the *arak* spirits and explores the sonic appearance of the spirits constructed within an interactive communication (Brinner 1995: 169, Norton 2000: 102) between spirit, medium and musicians.

¹ Khmer script is derived from some form of Brahmi script of South India (Huffman 1970: 4). Different scholars have transliterated this script in various forms. The transliteration I have adopted in this paper is based on the system used by Huffman (1970). Since some musical terms transliterated according to Huffman's system widely differ from the pronunciation, I have transliterated some key terms following the easier system made by some scholars of Khmer music (Brunet 1979, Commission de Musique 1969, Giuriati 1988, McKinley 2002) to facilitate the reading and comprehension of these key terms. Here is the list of terms as written by the just-mentioned scholars, with Huffman's versions presented in brackets: *arak* (*qaarəəq*); *bassac* (*baasaq*); *kar* (*kaad*); and *phleng* (*pleen*).

This paper aims to show the role of *phleng arak* music in structuring the ceremony and amusing the spirits. Moreover, it also contributes to broad the knowledge on Khmer rituals of possession which deserve more scholarly attention, since most Khmer music studies have been devoted to the classical music accompanying the Royal Ballet, traditional theatre genres, Buddhist ceremonies and the wedding music genres.

2. The *Arak* Spirit and the Khmer Health Cosmology

He [*arak*] was well known during the Hindu era, and his story is related to *Preah Pissnukaa*² the god protector of musicians and craftsmen. *Arak* was born during the Angkorian time [9th-15th century]. Angkor temples have been built thanks to *Preah Pissnukaa* and the *arak* spirit who was a sort of engineer. For example, he used red thread cotton to draw a kind of map of Angkor. He also organized the *Riep Preah Pissnukaa*, a ceremony for planning Angkor temples. At that time the *arak* was believed to be a person, but later he became a spirit because his power was no longer strong. He was in competition with *Priam*, the King's advisor, who was less able to predict the future. The *arak* could see things that others cannot; for example, when the king was sick the *arak* predicted his sickness and wrote its name on a sort of slab. Since the *arak* was a potent predictor, the king destroyed the *arak's* scripture to keep his secrets. However, the *arak's* foreseeable power has decreased over the years, and consequently, his predictions could be inaccurate. (Man Maen, interview, 13 October 2014)

This ethnographic snippet is an anecdote about the *arak's* role and magic powers, accounted by Man Maen, a *phleng arak* musician, and the decreasing trust in the *arak* spirits due to economic development and modernized healthcare services. In the past, *arak* spirits were considered to be doctors because they explain the causes of illness and reveal the cures. Nowadays, this belief is still alive in rural villages where health care service is less developed than in urban areas. Consultations of indigenous healers and spirit mediums are part of most people's everyday experience and considered, especially in the rural areas, as either alternative or supplementary treatment beside the treatment by biomedical practitioners.

Besides everyday hazards, illness in Cambodia can be caused by ancestors/spirits. The *arak* usually harms a person who does not observe the *arak's* rules and does not respect the societal conventions of their environment. For example, the *arak* can harm a person who picks fruit without asking permission:

People who visit the forest and steal fruits run a high risk of being punished. Around Angkor National park, the guards frequently collect some fruits, and consequently *arak* spirits punish them. Some of them die because they have not recovered from the illness

² In the Khmer cosmology, *Preah Pissnukaa* corresponds to the Hindu god Visvakarman who is considered to be the "architect of the universe" and god of craftsmen and musicians.

in time. So, when you are walking in a place where you are not the owner you have to ask permission before taking something. (Man Maen, interview, 06 October 2014)

If people do not show respect to the ancestors' spirits, the *arak* can punish them by causing illness. The term *arak* derives from the Sanskrit *ā-rakṣa* that means protector or guardian. They act as the moral guardians of society and they react to transgressions of social or moral norms by inflicting sickness on people (Ang 1986: 21-29). Therefore, sickness is caused by breaking morality through social actions. «As long as things are in order-in the social as well as in the natural and spiritual world-one can be at ease. But disorder breeds dis-ease» (Ovesen and Trankell: 283). It is in this context that the healer/spirit medium performs his art.

However, the *arak* is also defined as a *kaac* (nasty) spirit that resides in the forest, mountains and natural places, or in the proximity of villages. Therefore, the definition of the *arak* spirit is not so simple. Ang Choulean (1986) highlights the ambiguity of the term and the notion of *arak* which is often confused with that of *rāksasa* who is a kind of demon. According to Ang, the *arak* spirit belongs to both the savage *kmaoc priy* (spirits of the forest), who also embody the spirits of dead people, and to the *kmaoc srok* (spirits of the village). *Arak* spirit is also assimilated to the *yeaq* (giants), legendary characters considered as hostile semi-deities in India (Ang 1986: 117).

In Cambodia, *yeaq* are often protagonists of epic poems or *lkhaon bassac* theatre stories in which they play the role of tough and angry characters. Therefore, on the one hand, the *arak* is defined as savage and malevolent spirit who can harm people and once possessed, tell them their needs, particularly food, as the main reasons for their action is hunger. On the other hand, the *arak* is also considered to be a benevolent spirit and protector. For example, the *arak* can apparently protect a family lineage from bad spirits. In fact, it can happen that he/she is powerless against malevolent spirits; at the same time, he/she can get angry with one of their protected and cause illness. Therefore, *arak* has a dual nature as demon and protector.³

My informants, both mediums and musicians, distinguish different categories of *arak* spirit: territorial spirits, ancestors' spirits and master spirits. They can be either male or female; however, *kruu thom* (master spirits) are mostly male; the "king" of the big masters is called *Samdac Preah Kruu*. Others are territorial spirits or ancestors' spirits. Each *arak* has its name, for example, *Ta kung*, an ancestor's spirit, will declare his name when being caught through the music, then he claims some offers like banana, Khmer white wine and chicken. If the *arak* likes the offerings, he will leave the sick person. The *arak* spirits' names are the same across different geographic areas although there are some differences regarding ritual offerings and repertoires as shown in the following sections. The *arak*

³ Similarly, in other traditions, such as the Thai *Nora Rong Khru Chao Ban* ritual, ancestral spirits are believed to be demigods who can bless their family members if they are pleased, or punish those that have not observed their rules. See Parichat Jungwiwattanaporn 2006.

also explained the tools that are necessary for the next ceremony such as ritual objects, clothing, food, drink and even music. Spirits can manifest their personalities (through specific actions), simply speak to their descendants (explaining the reasons of the illness) or pass out good luck (blowing coconut juice or water).

The *coul ruup* ceremony is organized for multiple reasons, and the function of the *arak* within the ritual changes accordingly. The *arak* spirits can be recalled to ensure protection for their protected disciples, including the mediums. In this case, the ceremony does not involve healing, but the *arak* spits water or sprays perfume to purify the followers or some people who are particularly vulnerable to bad spirits. When the ceremony is for healing purposes, the *arak* spirit is interrogated to know the reasons of the illness and its remedies.

Besides having a healing purpose, the ceremony aims to gather family members once a year to maintain or strengthen their relationships; at the same time, it is for enjoyment as well as restoring broken relationships. Once per year on a pre-fixed date, between January and May, the medium or healed people have to organize the ritual of paying homage to the *arak* called *Laang Rooj*. They set a pavilion outside the house where the ceremony takes place. Even neighbours, friends and pupils are admitted to join the ceremony. They are villagers who have been recovered by *arak*; so, when the sun rises, they ask the medium to embody their healers (see Porèe-Maspero 1958, Ang 1986). In the past, during the night, the medium's relatives gathered in his or her house to reaffirm the family union and their relationship with the *arak*. I did not attend this ceremony during my fieldwork but, according to the mediums I interviewed, the *Laang Rooj* ceremonies are currently celebrated in the afternoon and last a few hours.

3. *Coul ruup* ceremony: participants

The first *coul ruup* ceremony I attended was on 24 January 2015 in Siem Reap province. I went to Man Maen's house at 2:45 pm.⁴ He is the leader of the *phleng arak* ensemble in his village. We travelled together by motorcycle to the ceremony and after a few minutes, we reached the medium's house. The ceremony was organized for healing purposes and for celebrating Mrs Man's mediumship. When we arrived, Mrs Man and a group of old ladies, her assistants, were preparing the offerings for the spirits. Successively, they placed the ritual objects and offerings in different settings according to the spirits' preferences and the *chaayam* [a genre accompanying Buddhist parades] drums close to the musicians. (Ethnographic snippets by the author)

Ruup (Medium)

Arak spirits communicate with human beings by possessing the body of a *ruup* and

⁴ Man Maen is a master of wedding (*phleng kar*) and *phleng arak* music and leader of a *phleng arak* ensemble in Siem Reap province. He is also my *tro ou's* (two-stringed fiddle) master.

building a sort of master-servant relationship. *Ruup* is a Khmer word from the Sanskrit *rupa* which means “shape,” “appearance” or “representation.” The *ruup* embodies the shape in which the spirits appear. The medium “performs various actions according to the inclination of the spirit within her” (Ebihara 1968: 437). In some provinces such as Kampong Spøi, the medium is called *meemut* or *snuał meemut* meaning «one who has many followers or students». ⁵ The *ruup* can be male or female even though the male medium is called *kruu* (Master/ teacher) ⁶ since the term *meemut* derives from the word *mee* that means woman. The *kru* practice by choice and of their own free will based on the spiritual and medical teaching they have received. Most of the *ruup* or *meemut*, on the contrary, become mediums against their own wishes as they are chosen by the spirits who appropriate their body for their own purpose.

The differences between female *ruup* and male *kruu* reflects the ideal Cambodian gender system, as detailed in the moral codes for men and women, *cbap proh* and *cbap srøy*, which were given literary shape in the early 19th century in the form of long poem (Ovesen and Trankell 2010: 148). According to *chbap*, women should be modest, submissive toward and honor their husbands, and let men make decisions on their behalf. ⁷

Here, I adopt the term *ruup* since it is the most common term for medium. According to a medium’s account, the *arak* usually chooses a *ruup* to possess by causing a high fever. The *ruup* dreams about the *arak* who reveals them to be their shape. The spirit prescribes the ritual objects, music and food preferences. Mediums, who have often been healed by the *arak*, consider that spirit as a master spirit (*kruu thom*) but the *arak* chooses few of them as their disciples (*koun säh*). ⁸ This liaison implies a relation of strong dependence, even an obsession, based on the observation of a sort of code of behaviour called *tra naam*. Each medium compiles a manual called *kumpii*. The *kumpii* contains the *tra naam* and mantras that the medium has been taught as well as his or her remedies and ritual procedures. This code is a sort of Holy Scripture jealously kept secretly by the *ruup*; sharing it with others would be to commit an offence to the teacher (*kruu thom*) and damage the healing power of the *ruup* and his/her *ksae* (lineage).

The mediumship is transmitted from generation to generation. To acquire this power an abstinence from doing or eating something is needed. By respecting and observing the *arak*’s precepts, mediums will be under the *arak*’s protection, but a medium who does not observe the prescribed rules might be punished by death. Once the *ruup* promises obedience to his/her *kruu thom*, he/she builds a sort of altar called *asna* in a suitable place of the house. At this point, the medium is healed and can cure patients. The *ruup* can

⁵ Bertrand (2004) uses the term *kruu boramey* to indicate a mediumship related to Buddhist practices.

⁶ Another term for male medium is *ta roonj* (Commission des Moeurs et Coutumes du Cambodge 1958: 69).

⁷ However, this does not mean that female mediums are devoid of practical agency. Rather, they assume a privileged position in the gendered system. The fact of having been chosen as a vehicle for a spirit allows her to claim a special status. This gives her a scope that most ordinary women do not have.

⁸ The term *säh/koun säh* (disciple) is quoted in Commission des Moeurs et Coutumes du Cambodge 1958 and Ang 1986.

FIGURE 1. A medium paying homage to her *Kruu Thom* (Master spirit) during a *coul ruup* ceremony in Siem Reap province, 24th January 2015 (photo F. Billeri).

FIGURE 2. The hierarchical relationship between supernatural and human spheres.

also embody other spirits which are called on behalf of sick people for consultation but only after having honoured his or her master spirit (Fig. 1). Therefore, there is a rigid hierarchy in the Khmer spirit cult system in which the *ruup* serves as a link between the non-human and the human beings (Fig. 2).

The communication between *arak* and *ruup* is called *klang* meaning “to communicate”, and it involves the former telling the latter the causes of the illness – usually a wrong doing – and suggesting an appropriate remedy.

Medium's Assistants

The assistants who attend to the possessee must interpret and facilitate the spirits' needs. Since assistants are usually also mediums, they have already learned to respond in particular ways to the *ruup* while possessed. They facilitate the communication between the possessee and the musicians and communicate with the spirits to ensure that the possession progresses smoothly. In the ceremonies I attended in Siem Reap province, up to four mediums were possessed in turn within the same ceremony. However, some of them played different roles at the same ceremony: ill person, medium's assistant and possessee.

The role of the assistant is to support the medium during the trance. Once they know which spirit is possessing the medium, they provide some objects related to that spirit(s) (clothing of different colours, particular ritual objects, and food). Successively, they interrogate them by asking questions about their health and economic situation,

and reporting questions from the followers who cannot speak directly to the spirits. Importantly, they also ask musicians for the songs requested by the spirits. Therefore, during the development of the ceremony, the mediums change roles, switching between patient, assistant and follower.

Musicians

Musicians are usually invited by the medium holding the *coul ruup* ceremony. The medium gives them money and gifts, and offers a meal before or after the ceremony. The musicians sit in a semi-circle next to the altar and the medium as they communicate with him or her during the different ritual phases. The *skɔɔ arak* (hand drum) players have the most important role of the *phleng arak* ensemble. The *skɔɔ arak* is a single-headed small goblet-shaped drum made of cobra or snake skin. A spot of tuning paste in the middle of the drum head allows playing different pitches. The rhythm of the *skɔɔ arak* facilitates the possession process by gradually increasing the tempo; Khmer musicians call this process *lieng skɔɔ* (fast *skɔɔ*). The number of *skɔɔ* ranges from two to twelve (Commission de Musique 1969) since the spirits are not only recalled by the fast rhythm but also by the *tyɔɔn* (heavy) timbre of the instruments.

The melodic instruments contribute to making the sound louder and more pleasant to the spirits. They include a *pey a* (double reed aerophone), *capey dong weng* (long-neck lute), *tro sao* (two-string fiddle with a cylindrical resonating chamber, similar to the Chinese *erhu*) and *tro ou* (lower-pitched two-string fiddle). Either *tro* or *pey a* “decorates” (*tan*) the melody depending on the confidence of the players. Some instruments such as the *pey pok* (bamboo flute) are used as a solo instrument, especially to recall spirits coming from mountainous regions. The composition of the ensemble varies slightly across different geographical areas.

For example, the ensemble Reak Smey Soriya in Kampong Spæi province used the *capey dong weng* instead of the *tro ou* which was employed in Siem Reap (Figs. 3-4). The *phleng arak* ensemble includes a singer, usually an old man. The singer can also be a drummer, and he has the duty of recalling the spirits by proffering clear words to address each spirit.

Audience

Phleng arak musicians primarily respond to the actions of the medium, rather than the audience, and do not usually modify musical phrases or the basic structure of songs in the course of performance but only change tempo and dynamics. Therefore, the audience behaviour does not affect the music performance as occurs in other traditions (Qureshi 1995).

In the *coul ruup* context musicians primarily respond to the actions of the medium, rather than the “audience.” In addition to the human audience members, the *arak* themselves can also be considered as a type of audience – embodied by the medium and responsive to music. This aspect is shown by some actions of the *ruup* such as turning

FIGURE 3. Man Maen's *phleng arak* ensemble playing during a *coul ruup* ceremony in Siem Reap province, 24th January 2015 (photo F. Billeri).

FIGURE 4. *Reak Smey Sorya* ensemble playing during a *coul ruup* ceremony in Kampong Spai province, 2nd May 2015 (photo F. Billeri).

the ear to the musicians, beating the tempo, clapping to express appreciation and signaling the musicians to play a faster rhythm. But, if the music does not satisfy the spirits' expectation, the medium stands and stares at the musicians.

The human audience of *coul ruup* generally comprises family members, fellow patients and even curious or concerned outsiders who observe the communication between the healer and the patient. They sit in front of or next to the altar and behind the medium and are not allowed to interact physically or verbally with them; they simply audit the ceremony and follow its development thanks to the relationship between music and spirits which articulates the possession ritual.

According to my impression, the audience enjoyed the ritual and were amused with the funny actions of some spirits. They laughed and observed the movements, gestures and actions of the spirits. By contrast, the spirits' physical involvement in the ritual sometimes scared them. For instance, it can happen that mediums point to one of the followers as the *arak* sees evil spirits, ghosts or other *arak* around. At this point, the follower is allowed to physically approach the medium to be "purified" through different treatments such as spraying perfume or applying beeswax on the followers' neck and back according to the medium's preferences. Some of the followers have a sort of master-servant relationship (*kruu coap snual*) with the master spirit. This relationship refers to a connection between the spirit and a person who recovered from an illness invoked by the spirit and then became a follower of the spirit. This relationship is hereditary and can remain so for many generations.

4. *Coul ruup* ceremony: structure

The ceremony took place outside the medium's house. The mediums set an altar on which were placed different offerings. A second altar called *kree preah thca* for master spirits was set outside the pavilion. Between the two altars, musicians were sitting around the *crooy*, a bowl made of rattan containing traditional Khmer sweets, tobaccos, incense sticks, a whole roasted chicken, soft drinks and some Khmer money (Ethnographic snippets by the author).

The medium is the ceremony's organizer who firstly starts the *arak* possession, and there are usually three or more mediums participating in a single ceremony. Mediums organize the *coul ruup* ceremony for different purposes. When the main objective is healing, the ritual is organized to find the reasons of the illness and its remedies (Figs. 5-6).

The length of the ceremony depends on the number of spirits involved. Although each medium has his or her master spirit, he/she can embody up to twenty-five more *araks*. Some *arak* spirits can take a night or even a day to enter a person. *Coul ruup* ceremonies occur between January and May before the start of the rainy season. "During these months they look for the reasons to possess a person to entertain themselves through the music and dance" (Man Maen, personal communication, 10 May 2015, Siem Reap). Recently, the number of ceremonies has decreased due to the individual economic situ-

FIGURE 5. A *coul ruup* ceremony in Siem Reap province, 24th January 2015 (photo F. Billeri).

FIGURE 6. A *coul ruup* ceremony for healing purposes in Siem Reap province, 24th January 2015 (photo F. Billeri).

Coul Ruup	Kampong Spə	Siem Reap
Pre-performance Ritual	1) <i>Pithii Twaay Preah Pissukaa</i> (Ritual of paying homage to Preah Pissukaa) ♪ = <i>Haom Rooy</i> (The sacred pavilion) 2) <i>Pithii Saen Ciidoun Ciitaa</i> (Ritual of offering to ancestors' spirits) ♪ = <i>Kong Saoy</i> (literally <i>kong</i> = "group"; <i>saoy</i> = "to eat")	<i>Pithii Roəm Chweeł Crooy</i> (Ritual of dancing around the <i>crooy</i>) ♪ = <i>Crooy Qanlong</i> (The shining <i>crooy</i>) ♪ = <i>Non Touc</i> (literally <i>non</i> = "aid/support"; <i>touc</i> = "small") ♪ = <i>Kok Krong</i> (The strong egret)
Post-performance Ritual (not performed for healing ceremonies)	1) <i>Pithii Twaay Phleng</i> (Ritual of offering music) ♪ = <i>phleng arak</i> and <i>phleng kar</i> songs 2) <i>Niət Mit Teəng Pram Pii Sandaan</i> (Inviting the extended family) ♪ = <i>Sampaw* Ciy</i> (Boat of victory)	Not Performed

* *Sampaw* refers to a small boat made of bamboo and leaves which represents an *arak* spirit's ritual object.

FIGURE 7. Pre-ritual and post-ritual performances, with connected songs in Siem Reap (S.R.) and Kampong Spəi (K.S.) provinces.

ation.⁹ However, people never give up their sacred vow even though they cannot afford to organize ceremonies.

The *arak* ceremony is composed of entry, middle and final section. Before the start and the end of the ceremony, musicians perform pre-rituals (Fig. 7). In Kampong Spəi they perform the *Pithii Twaay Preah Pissukaa* (Ritual of paying homage to *Preah Pissukaa*) by playing *Haom Rooy* (The sacred pavilion) to invite the masters of music¹⁰ and honor *Preah Pissukaa*, the god protector of musicians. This ritual is also performed before wedding ceremonies and theatre performances. In Siem Reap it is replaced by *Pithii Roəm Chweeł Crooy* (Ritual of dancing around the *Crooy*)¹¹ (Fig. 8) which is accompanied by *Crooy Qanlong* tunes played on the aerophone *pey pok*. These songs are also played to evoke the master spirits residing in mountainous regions (Fig. 9).

During the first stage of the ceremony, the "entering" section, musicians "explore" with different *phleng arak* songs until they find the appropriate and favorite song(s)

⁹ Healthcare is very expensive in Cambodia. The Cambodians have been exposed to two different medical practices and treatments ever since the French colonial government introduced the modern medicine in the late 19th century. Modern biomedicine and beliefs in animistic beliefs and practices have been existed in parallel with each other. People's choices of healthcare are primarily driven by pragmatic considerations such as economic, social and experiential and it is common for people to shift from modern medicine to traditional healing practices or using both simultaneously. The poorer and the further you live from and urban area, the lower the quality of the medical treatment you are likely to get and the greater the expenses in relation to your economic means.

¹⁰ "Master of music" refers to master spirits and it is not capitalised. The word "master" is capitalised for human master musicians.

¹¹ *Crooy* is an offering prepared by the medium specifically for the musicians. It consists of a bowl made of rattan containing traditional Khmer sweets, a bunch of bananas, tobaccos, incense sticks, candles, a whole roasted chicken, soft drinks and money. During the ritual, musicians sit in a circle around it.

FIGURE 8. The *croony* (photo F. Billeri).

of the *arak* spirits, as occurs in ritual traditions such as tarantism (de Martino [1961] 2006: 138). Although the rhythm is essential to excite the *arak* spirits and to provoke the possession, the melody serves as a “musical-motto” or “sung-theme” which identifies each spirit. In tarantism also, “musical mottoes” are used as a means of identifying the spider responsible for the possession, such as the tarantula wolf spider in Italy or the scorpion in Sardinia (*argia*) which is thought to cause the patient’s illness. The treatments vary according to the different kinds of tarantula or *argia* (the widow, the nubile and the wife).

The success of this music “exploration” depended on the skill of the musicians, as did the efficacy of the cure, once the “right music” has been found (de Martino [1961] 2006: 214). Carpitella observes that «the single *tarantati* are stimulated to dance only by one of these keys [A major, D major, B minor, and A minor] while others remain indifferent to others» (Carpitella [1961] 2006: 299). Just as each spider is believed to have its own taste in tunes, so it is with the *arak*. Consequently, the repertoire contains a traditionalized series of tunes and songs from which one must choose the one (or ones) best suited to each particular case. However, the mediums themselves understand which song should be performed to be possessed quickly.

The number of the songs normally played in a ceremony depends on places (particularly the place where the musicians are invited the first time), offerings and spirits. Once the *arak* possesses the medium, he/she declares the name so that the musicians know which songs should be subsequently performed for each type of *arak*. After the

FIGURE 9. A *pey pok* (flute) layer is recalling a spirit residing in mountainous regions during a *coul ruup* ceremony in Siem Reap province, 25th January 2015 (photo F. Billeri).

possession the spirit can request other songs and the middle section starts. This is the time for the medium to explain the reasons for the illness and answer the questions of the *arak's* followers; they ask about health, success and even lottery numbers. Mediums can do different ritual actions to cure or bless people according to the main aim of the ceremony.

During the ceremonies in Siem Reap, mediums usually danced, ate, smoked, chewed betel leaves and slapped banana tree stems on the floor. In Kampong Spøi, except for one ceremony where the mediums embodied a monkey's spirit, they did not dance but applied beeswax on the followers' neck who in turn knelt down on the ground. In both provinces mediums spat coconut juice from their mouths, considered a pure liquid, and sprayed perfume from a bottle on the followers' bodies to keep away negative influences. The musicians continued playing songs which were not specific to the possession process but serve mainly to entertain the spirits. In the last section of the ceremony (*sdah*), the spirit leaves the medium. Specific ritual actions of the medium such as falling on the floor, shaking the *ptull*¹² or covering his/her face with a hand, signal the *sdah* (exit of the spirit). Then the medium looks dazed, not knowing what occurred during the possession¹³ (Fig. 10).

¹² A small round footed silver tray for holding ritual objects used by the medium.

¹³ See Guelden (2007: 165) for a similar process in *Nora* dance-drama performance in Southern Thailand.

Structure of the Ceremony	Ritual	Song
Entering (<i>coul</i>)	Mediums shake their body; they proclaim the name of the <i>arak</i> spirit(s).	Music “exploration” or songs requested by medium
Middle Section (Interrogation; healing; blessing)	Mediums can do different actions: dancing, eating, wearing clothes of different colours, smoking, chewing betel leaves, applying powder on their face, applying beeswax on the people’s neck, slapping two banana leaf stems, blowing water.	Songs to entertain the spirit(s) from <i>phleng arak</i> or other genres including the <i>phleng kar</i> repertoire
Exit (<i>sdab</i>)	Mediums fall; cover their face with their hand; sit down saying “I am going out.”	No specific songs
Final Rituals (musicians only)	1) <i>Pithii Croonj</i> or <i>Saa Roonj</i> (S.R.) (Ritual of dismantling the pavilion) 2) <i>Pithii Saa Pidaan</i> (S.R.) (Ritual of dismantling the ceiling) 3) <i>Beh Pkaa Twaay Kruu</i> (K.S.) (Ritual of collecting flowers)	♪ = <i>Kok Krong</i> (S.R.) (The strong egret) ♪ = <i>Saa Sapbaay</i> (S.R.) (literally <i>saa</i> = “to roll up” and <i>sapbaay</i> = “happiness”) ♪ = <i>Beh Pkaa</i> or <i>Beh Phlae Cəə</i> (K.S.) (Collecting flowers or collecting fruit) ♪ = <i>Saang Vaa Phleng</i> (K.S.) (Music for ending the ceremony)

FIGURE 10. General structure of *coul ruup* ceremony. The abbreviation “K.S.” is for Kompong Spəi province and “S.R.” for Siem Reap province. When the abbreviation is not specified the ritual/song is performed in both provinces.

At the end of the *coul ruup* ceremony, musicians perform post-rituals. In Siem Reap, the ceremonies ended with *Saa Roonj* (Dismantling the pavilion) or *Croam* ritual the latter of which was accompanied by the song called *Kok Krong* (The strong egret). It was followed by the *Saa Pidaan* (Ritual of rolling the ceiling)¹⁴ accompanied by the *Saa Sapbaay* song (literally *saa* means “to roll something up” and *sapbaay* means “happiness”) (Fig. 11).

In Kampong Spəi, the final ritual was *Beh Pkaa Twaay Kruu* (Ritual of collecting the flowers) for the masters of music. This ritual was accompanied by *Beh Pkaa* (Collecting flowers), also known as *Beh Phlae Cəə* (Collecting fruit). Fruits symbolically represent happiness throughout Cambodia; one of the musicians, usually the oldest of the group, collects some fruits tied to the altar by a string, then gives the fruits to the medium on behalf of the spirit. The *Beh Phlae Cəə* ritual is performed when the ceremony is for master spirits. Both the *Saa Pidaan* and the *Beh Pkaa Twaay Kruu* rituals signal the end of the *coul ruup* ceremony.

The *coul ruup* ceremony is framed by rituals conducted before and after, in which the musicians are the protagonists of the ritual action. They perform some pre-*coul ruup* rituals to honor the master of music; rituals to recall and invite particular types of *arak* spirits such as ancestral family spirits and master spirits; and post-performance rituals that signal the end of the ceremony. Specific songs correspond to each of these rituals.

¹⁴ *Pidaan* refers to a sort of ceiling made of a white cotton fabric from which betel leaves hang. It is set if the *arak* ceremony’s purpose is to get rid of malevolent spirits.

FIGURE 11. *Saa Pidaan* Ritual (Dismantling the ceiling) during a *coul ruup* ceremony in Siem Reap province, 24th January 2015 (photo F. Billeri).

5. The musical repertoire

As discussed above, the *phleng arak* repertoire includes songs which are connected to preliminary and final rituals performed by the musicians. Interestingly, pre-ritual songs not only precede *coul ruup* ritual but are also performed before every wedding ceremony and theatre performance as an offering to deities and a means for recalling supernatural spirits:

The Khmers regard music as an offering, in the same way as an incense stick or a bouquet of flowers placed in a sanctuary. To make an offering of music to the Divinities enables one to acquire “merit” in a future life. (Brunet 1974: 219)

The music itself is considered as an offering to gods and supernatural beings; this is the reason why Khmer musicians say that music must be played “beautifully.” In the *coul ruup* context, pre-rituals and final rituals signal the start and end of the ceremony. Also, specific songs are played according to the different stages of the possession and each category of spirit. For each ceremony, the repertoire includes approximately ten/twelve songs that can be repeated if the same spirits are recalled. It is possible to distinguish between songs for master spirits and among them, songs for the head of the master spirits, *Somdac Preah Kruu*; songs for territorial spirits living in the forest, mountainous and natural places; songs for ancestors’ spirits residing in the house and related to a particular member of the family.

The *araks* can also request additional songs; these songs are borrowed from different genres such as *chaayam*, a musical genre played for the parades and Buddhist festivals, or music accompanying traditional and modern dance such as *roəm vong*¹⁵ and *saaraavan*. For example, during a ceremony in Siem Reap, the mediums requested the presence of *chaayam* instruments before the ceremony to meet the spirit’s requirement (Fig. 12). The spirit enjoyed the music very much. She danced and played the small gong ([Video 1](#)).

Musicians adapted the *arak* song to the *chaayam* genre. This phenomenon of adaptation is also discussed by Norton (2009) regarding the “*chau van-ization*” of songs from other genres. Two musicians, who did not belong to the *phleng arak* ensemble, played the typical *chaayam* drums. The *skɔɔ arak* players followed the *chaayam* rhythm by playing on the *arak* drums to make the sound louder while a young boy danced by playing a small gong and cymbals with the medium in the middle of the ritual scene.

The insertion of “extra-songs” in a possession ceremony is also common to other cultures such as the Korean shamanic rituals called *kut*. In the central section of the ritual, the *mudang* (ritualist) performs a miscellany of songs and dances of either secular or religious content for entertaining the clients. These songs include the performance of folksongs and songs from the *p’ansori* repertoire, popular ballads and sometimes even pop songs. Longer insertable narrative songs and comic drama episodes may be included in longer rituals (Mills 2007: 22). However, in the Korean ritual, these songs serve to entertain the clients, and they are played in the central section of the fixed structure of the ceremony, while in the Khmer *coul ruup* ritual they are played when requested by the *arak* spirits for entertaining themselves since they are not included in the ceremony structure. Therefore, not all the rituals include these additional repertoires. In other words, musicians play at the *araks*’ command, and these repertoires have the function of amusing the spirit only.

The same phenomenon occurs in other Southeast Asian rituals. For example, in the

¹⁵ *Roəm vong* means “dancing in circle”. It is danced around a table decorated with flowers and fruits. This dance is still performed at wedding parties, Khmer New Year celebrations and every occasion in which family or friends gather for a party or event.

FIGURE 12. A medium dancing *chaayam* music during a *coul ruup* ceremony in Siem Reap province, 24th January 2015 (photo F. Billeri).

Thai *phi mod* ceremony in Northern Thailand musicians switch to perform from the traditional *piphat mon* style to the modern “popular” tunes in the *dontri phuen muang* style to attract the dead spirits who are unfamiliar with the traditional style (Shahriari 2006: 72-73). Similarly, in the Burmese *nat pwe* rituals, different repertoires are performed: traditional songs are strictly related to the spirit’s (*nat*) identity and are conducted to recall them while new compositions including Burmese popular music have the function of entertaining the spirits during the possession (Chiarofonte 2014: 19-20).

The *phleng arak* texts aim to evoke and recall the spirits by mentioning their name and their story. If the song texts are not appropriate, the *arak* is not satisfied. One of the mediums, after the possession, told me that the spirit was unhappy with the music as the song text did not mention his story. However, most of the songs I recorded in Siem Reap are instrumental since the spirits are also able to recognize the tunes very well. In the absence of texts, more attention is paid to the “quality” of the performance as a medium emphasizes: «If spirits do not like the performance, they do not possess the medium».¹⁶

6. Musical features of the *phleng arak* genre

Liən Skəə (Fast Drum)

People from the village and mediums’ relatives gathered around the first medium who was sitting in front of the altars. The musicians started to play *Srəy Kmaw* (“Black Lady”). The medium, a disabled old lady, was listening to the loud melody and following the fast

¹⁶ Medium, interview, 5 March 2015.

rhythm of the *skɔɔ arak* by beating her hand against her leg and rhythmically shaking her head and torso until the spirit possessed her ([Video 2](#)).

Phleng arak songs do not have rhythmic patterns or set sequences of songs that are specific to each particular *arak*, as is the case with the Vietnamese *chau van* songs (Norton 2000) and the Burmese *nath saing* songs (Chiarofonte 2014). Rather, the songs are chosen by mediums who usually already know which spirit will possess them. Increasing the tempo of *phleng arak* music has a key functional role in the *arak* possession. In *phleng arak* music it is relatively easy to perceive that the tempo increases significantly as soon as the spirit possesses the medium. Khmer musicians define this process of rhythm acceleration as *liən skɔɔ* (fast drum).

The possessee matches the musician's increase in tempo by swinging her head back and forth with correspondingly faster and more vigorous movements. When the songs rhythm changes in response to the medium's movements, there is little or no song choice, so musicians usually know which song will be performed. Movement is coordinated with the rhythm of music during the dance, but even when mediums are seated their bodily movements are musically regulated. They swing their arms, sway their torsos, drink, smoke, utter words and interact with the ensemble and followers in ways that are musically coordinated. Musicians speed up the rhythm when the spirit possesses the medium, and it gradually increases while the medium dances, heals, blesses. The music stops when the medium sits, falls on the floor or raises her/his hand.

Therefore, rhythmic patterns are repeated across the whole repertoire. By contrast, Mills describes the rhythmic variants to attract the listeners in the Korean *kut* ritual:

Musicians are not merely playing a fixed pattern ad infinitum; they are selecting rhythmic variants from a mental stores reservoir, aiming to create musical interest by playing with the listeners' expectation while creating subtle fluctuations in the music's dynamic flow. (Mills 2003: 238)

In the *coul ruup* context, the "addressee" of the rhythm is the spirit. It can happen that the medium signals to the ensemble to play a quicker rhythm by beating the tempo on her leg faster and faster and shaking her arms and head vigorously, for example. Starting from Rouget's idea of the temporal aspect of the possession musics, Jankowsky (2010), in his study of *Štambēli* in Tunisia, considers the ritual dynamics of musical time: «In *Štambēli*, gradual and multifaceted transformations in both musical time and sonic density work synergically to create a sense of directed motion» (Jankowsky 2010: 113). This sense of musical direction evidenced by the repetitive and cyclic nature of this music can also be perceived in *phleng arak* music in terms of tempo and sound volume.

Jankowsky also examines the parameters of the process of acceleration to account for how musicians decide tempo changes on any given *nuba* (tune). He examines two main conditions: 1) the presence or not of a dancer) the place of *nuba* within a *silsila* (a

sequence of *nuba*) and its rhythmic pattern (no correlation between the length of a *nuba* and the acceleration). Since the *phleng arak* tunes are not played within sequences, there is some flexibility in starting and ending the tempo while when a tune is played as a part of a sequence, such as the *nuba*, musicians must balance the process of acceleration within the sequence.

Fig. 13 shows how the tempo of *phleng arak* song gradually increases in the course of the ritual according to the medium's action. The fastest part is connected to specific actions such as dancing, blessing, healing while the slowest part signals the beginning of the song, when the spirit is recalled. The rhythm decreases at the end of the song during the exit of the spirit or at the end of the possession (Video 3).¹⁷

In the *phleng arak* repertoire the same drum music works for all the spirits and is impersonal in a way it does not function as a "musical motto" as it is the case of the melody.

The "heavy" timbre of *phleng arak* "roads"

The medium, an old lady, sprayed perfume on the monk who was sitting on a deck chair; then she signaled the musicians to stop playing by raising her hand and asked for another song called *Tummeāk Damriy* (Hunter with the elephant). *Tummeāk Damriy* is a hunter spirit accompanied by an elephant. Once the spirit possessed the medium, she was given a wooden stick with two bunches of banana, two bottles of water and *nom koom*¹⁸ attached on its poles. She carried the wooden stick on her shoulder as the *arak* was hunting, sometimes she turned her ears to the musicians; the drum beats increased in tempo and the volume of the melodic *plaw* (roads)¹⁹ rose once she approached the ensemble. She threw a bottle of water to the musicians. Then the spirit checked to see if the offerings, particularly the chicken, were placed appropriately in a *croon* (a rattan basket). Successively, musicians played *Srøy Kmaw* (The black lady) song for the second time, and a lady close to her held up a *kramaa*²⁰ to welcome the spirit. Then she asked for the song called *Sampooy*. After a few minutes, the spirit left her body. (Ethnographic snippets by the author)

The efficacy of the rhythmic pattern to induce the possession is not only due to the changing of tempo but also to a variation of timbre and volume of each sound (Mills 2003: 252). «Acceleration of tempo very often goes hand in hand with an intensification of sound» (Rouget 1985: 82). *Phleng arak* tunes are divided into two main melodic phrases called *thaat* (drawers-of-spirits) that are the conduit by which the spirit enters/leaves the medium's body. The songs are divided into two sections each with a different character and tempo: the first section is played before the possession and is called *qah kamlang*

¹⁷ Fig. 13 illustrates the gradual tempo changes related to the ritual actions of *Srøy Kmaw* and *Sampooy* songs. I have chosen to report these two songs as the ritual actions were similar and easier to compare. However, other *phleng arak* songs would follow the same essential pattern.

¹⁸ Traditional Khmer sweet made of sticky rice wrapped in banana leaves.

¹⁹ *Plaw* is an indigenous term used to explain the process of improvisation called *bamphlay* (taking different roads). The term *plaw* (roads) indicates the different versions of the melody.

²⁰ *Kramaa* is a traditional Khmer scarf especially used in the countryside. It is also used as towel and hat.

(tired; listlessly) in a slower tempo and a softer volume obtained through playing in a lower octave; the second section is played after the possession and is called *klang* (loud) which is characterized by a faster rhythm and a louder sound called *kaac* (nasty). The medium was very responsive to the loud volume of the song.

In addition to the rhythm and dynamics, musicians pay attention to the aesthetic and the “quality” of the performance. For this reasons they said, «if we do not play music beautifully the *arak* does not enter.» According to Khmer musicians, “playing beautifully” means embellishing the melody by adding notes to “make the sound beautiful.” To accomplish this, they adopt a technique called *tik daam* (sweet water) that is a sort of tremolo played on melodic instruments. Each instrument has a different way of playing *tik daam*; Maw Yon, a *phleng arak* musician, for example, showed me how to play *tik daam* on the *ksaediaw* (plucked monochord) by bouncing the sound box made of a half gourd close to his chest. This technique is defined as *rɔlaek* (bouncing). Sometimes *tik daam* is executed by plucking the one string according to a technique called *rum njə* (plucking). It is a technique that every musician has to be good at since the ability of a musician is judged in accordance with his skills at embellishing the melody:

Cambodian music requires a lot of imagination, initiative and inventiveness from the musicians, because a good performance does not consist of following step-by-step and faithfully a composition, but rather to decorate, garnish, enrich, and embellish the composition with techniques, ways of playing, and styles that reveal more than the musician’s training, his personality and character. (Commission de Musique 1969: 139)

A skilled musician continuously “embellishes” the melody with slight or greater melodic and rhythmic variations according to the instrument’s features, the musician’s background, the performance context and his own “style.” Various musical cultures of Southeast Asia have a number of features in common such as a process of musical and rhythmic elaboration of a fixed melody and its abstraction (Hood 1975: 26). While in other musical cultures of Southeast Asia the improvisation is based on a fixed melody explicitly performed by an instrument or from a family of instruments, such as the Javanese gamelan, in which the fixed melody is played by the metallophones *saron* and for the Balinese gamelan in which the melody is performed by the *jublag* or *jegogan* (lowest-register metallophones), in Khmer music the fixed melody consists of the succession of notes played by all instruments in correspondence with the damped strokes of the *ching* (cymbals), and for such reason can be defined as “abstract melody” or implicit, while in Java it has a specific name, *balungan*, and in Bali *pokok*.

Sumarsam (1975) defines it as “inner melody”, referring not to a pre-established common model, but a model resulting from the sum of the different versions of a given internal melody performed by different musicians; it is an “accumulated memory” of different performances (Benamou 1989: 553). However, Benamou considers the slippery concept of the *balungan* in his analysis on Solonese music. The fixed melody tends to

FIGURE 13. Tempo changes of *Srəy Kmav* (The black lady) and *Samponj* (Casula hairdo) according to specific ritual actions.

conform closely to the *bonang*, *saron*, and *slenthem* parts, whereas the “inner melody” tends to follow the *rebab*, the *gendèr*, and the *gambang*. The two *balungans* – the notated one and the *rebab*-like melody – usually converge at important structural points, as do all of the instrumental and vocal parts in general. In this sense, they are essentially “the same” for a Javanese musician. Occasionally, however, they diverge temporarily at these points. There is a sense, in other words, in which the notated melody is a distorted “inner melody,” adjusted so as to make a nice *saron* and *bonang* part (each instrument of the gamelan is sometimes said to translate the *balungan* into its own language) (*ibid.*: 175). Similarly, a *phleng arak* musician, defined the variations of the melody *praliy bat phleng* (distortion).²¹

Khmer musicians do not have a specific terminology to describe the continuous variation process, but use the term *bamphlay* (Giuriati 1995) to refer to the improvisation process, from *plaw* “road”. They explain the process of improvisation through the metaphor of travelling: «at the beginning we play normally and then we take one road (*tiw plaw muəy*) but when the *arak* enters we change road (*kae*). *Tik daam* is used to take the different roads» (Man Maen, interview, 08 October 2014, Siem Reap). Playing the melody was compared to following or creating a road (*plaw*). In ensemble playing there would be as many different roads as melodic instruments/singers. All of the musicians would be “traveling” in the same direction but each would take a slightly different path, meeting up periodically with all of the others before branching off again.

Some scholars describe this uniqueness of each variation in other musical traditions in a similar way. For instance, Witzleben (1995) examines the heterophonic processes present in Chinese music which is explained by Chinese musicologists through the metaphor of *zhisheng fudiao* (“branch sound polyphony”) which resembles small branches of a river that continually diverge from the main stream and then return to it (Witzleben 1995: 106). Furthermore, Sutton (1982) focuses on the variation in the performance of Central Javanese gamelan music. He analyses the difference among musicians’ renditions

²¹ Maw Yon, personal communication, 10 June 2015.

of a piece which is referred to as “individual variation” (Sutton 1982: 246-247). As a result, during my *tro ou* lessons, Man Maen continually changed the melody I was learning from lesson to lesson since he did not want to teach me only one “road.” In Khmer music variations are embedded in the concept of melody.

“The interactive system”

From the analysis of the ceremony and the musical features emerges an important aspect of *coul ruup* ritual which is the interaction between the medium and the ensemble. Starting from Brinner’s analytical concepts – interactive network, interactive system, interactive sound structure, and interactive motivation – Norton (2009) frames the discussion of the performative interactions during *len dong* ritual of possession in Vietnam. These concepts are defined by Brinner (1995) as follows: “Interactive network” concerns the roles assumed by musicians and their relationships or links; the “interactive system” refers to the means and meanings of communication and co-ordination; and the “interactive sound structure” is a constellation of concepts associated with the constraints and possibilities inherent in the ways sounds are put together (Brinner 1995: 169).

While Brinner’s study refers to the interaction between musicians, Norton (2000) adapts Brinner’s interaction theory to the *chau van* music, accompanying the *len dong* ritual of possession in Vietnam, by including to the analytical framework of musical interaction performers other than musicians such as the medium. This aspect of interaction is also mentioned by Brac de la Perrière (1989: 129) relating to the *nat pwe* ritual in Burma and it also occurs in *coul ruup* rituals in Cambodia.

On the one hand, the interaction between musicians is based on what Brinner calls “network interaction”: «A good musician and a good performer is by Khmer standards the one who holds musical dialogue and interacts with the other musicians of the ensemble» (Giuriati 1988: 260). On the other hand, as Norton pointed out, the interaction also occurs between the medium and the ensemble. While *chau van* music is organized in sequences of songs corresponding to specific kinds of spirits, *phleng arak* songs are chosen by the medium who usually knows which spirit will possess him/her. Therefore, the medium is a sort of conductor of the ensemble who requires specific songs. Through a system that links songs to ritual actions and spirits, different songs are performed at each stage of possession. Brinner (1995) defines a cue as «a musical, verbal, visual, or kinetic act specifically produced to initiate an interaction – that is, bringing about a change in the performance of others in the ensemble – that would not occur otherwise» (Brinner 1995: 183).

The medium communicates with the ensemble by raising a hand to stop them, by beating the tempo, clapping the hands to express appreciation of the music or, on the contrary, staring at the musicians or standing to express dislikes. All of these instances of “mediation cues” (*ibid.*: 188-189) are interesting examples of communication between the medium and musicians. Movement is coordinated with the rhythms of music during dances, but even when mediums are seated, their bodily movements are musically

regulated. Similarly, in other Southeast Asian rituals such as the *Nora* ritual in Southern Thailand «the spirits use the medium's body to answer questions about offerings (cry, hug, and dance)» (Guelden 2007: 162).

Another type of interaction is that between musical instruments and the possessee. Rouget (1985) examines how the relation between musicians and possessees operate at the individual level and group level. The latter is common to the *coul ruup* ceremony since musicians do not bring their instrument close to the medium's ears as happened in other traditions, except for some kinds of mountainous spirits who are recalled by the sound of the flute *pey pok*. Only on this occasion does a musician bring his instrument close to the medium's ear and play melodies to facilitate the possession.

An additional peculiar aspect of the *coul ruup* ceremony is the role of the audience. In some traditions, the audience actively participates in the ceremony and interacts with the medium and musicians. Regula Qureshi describes a phenomenon she calls “music-context interaction” (Qureshi 1995 [1986]: 140). Her analysis of Qawwali events focuses on the “interplay between music and audience behaviour” and demonstrates how musicians change their performances in order to increase the ecstatic arousal of the audience (*ibid.*: 143). In the *coul ruup* context musicians primarily respond to the actions of the medium, rather than the “audience.” In fact, they do not usually modify musical phrases or the core structure of songs in the course of performance but only change tempo and sound volume. In *coul ruup* rituals, the spirits can also be considered as a type of audience.

This aspect is shown by some actions of the medium such as turning the ear to musicians, beating the tempo with a hand, clapping to express his/her appreciation of the music (Fig. 14, [Video 4](#)); on the contrary, if the music does not satisfy her expectation he/she stands to stare at the musicians. Therefore, although the medium does not have any musical knowledge, he/she does interact with the ensemble, conduct it and express his/her likes and dislikes through the use of a range of cues (Fig. 15). *Phleng arak* not only “translates” into sounds and ritual actions the appearance of the spirits but also connects and conjoins the human and supernatural spheres through an interactive communication between spirits, medium and musicians.

7. Final remarks

In the *coul ruup* context, music is essential since it has not only the function of recalling the spirits but also satisfying their requests. Each spirit has its identification song, dancing style, gestures and song texts which can vary slightly according to the geographic area, the singer and the ensemble. Therefore, songs are related to particular spirits but they are not structured as melodic or rhythmic sequences as occurs in other Southeast Asian musical traditions. Each medium can be possessed by the same *arak*. Therefore, the same songs can be continually repeated. Moreover, the insertion of extra-repertoires depends on the *arak* spirit's requests and it does not always occur. Similarly, dance does not always occur

FIGURE 14. A medium embodying the “black lady” approaching the musicians to listen to the drums beat during a *coul ruup* ceremony in Siem Reap province, 24th January 2015 (photo F. Billeri).

since some mediums do not like dancing or cannot dance due to their physical condition. It also depends on the geographic area where the ceremony takes place. For example, mediums in Kampong Spøi province did not dance and musicians knew in advance the songs to play while in Siem Reap province mediums always danced and musicians played the songs requested by the medium or their assistants by voice or they found the “right song” through a “music exploration”.

The lively character of the *arak* spirits is reflected in their funny gestures and actions, and it is translated into sound by the *phleng arak* music. Rhythms do not vary according to the gender, ethnicity or type of spirit as in other musical traditions, but the most remarkable features of the *phleng arak* music are the progressive intensification of the sound, acceleration of tempo and the “quality” of the performance. The faster the rhythm and the louder the sound, the easier the spirit “enters” (*coul*). The drums lead the ensemble and the melodic instruments contribute to producing an intense and loud sound by playing in their high registers. The loudness and fast tempo are two essential characteristics of this music as they not only facilitate the possession and accompany the medium’s dance and gestures but also entertain and amuse the spirit possessed by the medium who conducts the ensemble to play faster and louder through specific visual signals. The gradual

AMUSING THE SPIRITS THROUGH THE MUSIC

Cues	Mediums' Actions and Their Meaning	Musicians' Action
Visual	Shaking the <i>ptull</i> = spirit possession	Changing of tempo
	Sitting down/Passing hand on face = exit of the spirit	Stop playing
	Approaching musicians = checking the offerings	Faster rhythm and louder sound volume
Verbal	Asking for the song = identification of the spirit	Playing the required song
Musical	Beating a faster tempo = recalling the spirit	Playing a faster tempo
	Turning the ear to musicians = "checking" the song	Playing louder
Kinetic	Raising the hand= stop musicians from playing	Stop playing
	Clapping hands = enjoyment of the music	Keeping a fast tempo and a loud sound
	Shaking body and head = possession	Increasing tempo and sound volume
	Dancing = possession	Increasing tempo and sound volume

FIGURE 15. "Mediation cues" summary.

acceleration of the rhythm and *crescendo* of sound occur during and after the possession, in the healing phase; tempo increases when the medium, for example, shows her/his attention to the song by turning the ear to musicians or approaching them.

This paper constitutes a first classification and analysis of the *phleng arak* repertoire focusing on the features strictly connected to the possession stage and the nature of the *arak* spirits. The analysis of the relationship between *coul ruup* rituals and *phleng arak* music shows how the sonic appearance of the spirits is constructed within an interactive communication between spirit, medium and musicians, and the role of music which not only facilitates the possession and is connected to ritual action but also entertains the spirits who become a type of audience responsive to music.

Tempo	Ritual Action	Video Timings
91 beats/min.	Asking for Srey Kmaw song and waiting for the spirit possession	00:00:02–00:01:13
125 beats/min.	Wearing red clothes connected to the black lady spirit/clapping the tempo	00:01:14–00:03:02
160–165 beats/min.	Blessing the monk	00:03:03–00:03:59
135 beats/min. (rallentando)	Raising the hand (music ends)	00:04:00–00:04:12

FIGURE 16. The medium's sequence of actions during the different phases of the possession with the corresponding tempo changes (see Video 2).

Tempo	Ritual Action	Video Timings
88.9 beats/min.	Listening to music	00:00:00–00:00:22
126.2 beats/min.	Possession (medium shakes her head, torso and beats the tempo)	00:00:23–00:00:33
157 beats/min.	Dance	00:00:33–00:03:11
186–193 beats/min.	Approaching the monk/blessing the monk	00:03:12–00:04:33
201.5 beats/min.	Dance	00:04:34–00:06:07
139.2 beats/min.	Exit of the spirit (sitting down, shaking the <i>ptull</i>)	00:06:08–00:06:14

FIGURE 17. Tempo changes and their connection with the ritual action (see Video example 3).

Multimedia Contents

Videos

The videos attached to this article are based on fieldwork carried out by myself in different provinces of Cambodia on a doctoral fieldwork award from SOAS University of London in 2015. Since the article is structured around a performance-oriented analysis of *coul ruup* rituals, I examine the remarkable features of *phleng arak* music connected to the possession by analyzing four videos extracts from a ceremony I filmed in Wat Rajabo village (Siem Reap province) on 24th January 2015 (I used a Canon MINI-DV camcorder). The musical performance was carried out by the “Man Maen’s ensemble” composed by Man Maen (*tro kmae*, three-stringed fiddle, and *tro ou*, two-stringed fiddle), Lonh Samnang (*tro sao*, two stringed-fiddle), Men Pring (*pey a*, double-reeded oboe), Men Supheak (*tro ou*, two-stringed fiddle), Men Borey (*skɔɔ arak*, hand drums), Man Moeun (*skɔɔ arak*), and Um Chhoeun (*skɔɔ arak*).

1. [Chayaam music](#) [2:50].

This video shows a medium dancing *chayaam* music on the behalf of the spirit during a *coul ruup* ceremony.

2. [Srɔy Kmaw \(The black lady\)](#) [4:09].

This video shows a medium with her assistants asking musicians to play *Srɔy Kmaw* before the possession. Fig. 16 illustrates the medium’s sequence of actions during the different phases of the possession with the corresponding tempo changes showed in the video.

3. [Sampooŋ song \(Casual hairdo\)](#) [6:24].

This video shows a medium paying homage to her master spirit (*Kruu thom*) and dancing while being possessed on *Sampooŋ* song to show the gradual increase of the rhythm of *phleng arak* songs as showed in Fig. 17.

4. [The medium listening to Tummeāk Damriy song \(The Hunter with the elephant\)](#) [1:49].

This video shows a medium listening to *Tummeāk Damriy* song showing enjoyment and appreciation for the music especially the rhythm of the drums.

Multimedia contents are available
via QR code

References

- Ang, Chouléan
 1986 *Les êtres surnaturels dans la religion populaire Khmère*, Paris, Cedorek.
- Benamou, Marc
 2010 *Rasa: Affect and Intuition in Javanese Musical Aesthetics*, Oxford, Oxford University Press.
- Bertrand, Didier
 2000 “Pratique Médiumnique de possession au Cambodge”, in Denise Aigle, Bénédicte Brac de la Perrière, and Jean-Pierre Chaumeil (eds.), *La politique des esprits: Chamanismes et religions universalites*, Nanterre, Société d’ethnologie: 125-147.
 2004 “A Medium Possession Practice and Its Relationship with Cambodian Buddhism. The Gru Pāramī”, in Elizabeth Guthrie and John Marston (eds.), *History, Buddhism and New Religious Movements in Cambodia*, Honolulu, University of Hawai’i Press: 150-247.
- Billeri, Francesca
 2022 “The Interrelations of Genre in Traditional Cambodian Music and Theatre”, *European Journal of Musicology*, XX/1: 243-268.
- Brac de La Perrière, Bénédicte
 1989 *Les rituels de possession en Birmanie: du culte d’État aux cérémonies privées*, Paris, Recherche sur les civilisations.
- Brinner, Benjamin E.
 1995 *Knowing Music, Making Music: Javanese Gamelan and the Theory of Musical Competence and Interaction*, Chicago, University of Chicago Press.
- Brunet, Jacques
 1974 “Music and Rituals in Traditional Cambodia”, in Mohd. Taib Osman (ed.), *Traditional Drama and Music of Southeast Asia*, Kuala Lumpur, Dewan Bahasa: 219-222.
 1979 “L’orchestre de mariage cambodgien et ses instruments”, *Bulletin de l’Ecole Française d’Extrême-Orient*, 66: 203-254.
- Carpitella, Diego
 2006 “The Choreutic-Musical Exorcism of Tarantism” [1961], in de Martino 2006: 286-315.
- Catlin, Amy
 1987 *Apsara: the Feminine in Cambodian Art: an Exhibition and Publication on the Arts of Cambodian Women in Los Angeles area*, Los Angeles, the Woman’s Building.
- Chiarofonte, Lorenzo
 2014 “Nat Hsaing: Musiche per i culti di possessione in Birmania”, *Quaderni Asiatici*, CVIII: 5-36.
- Commission des Moeurs et Coutumes du Cambodge
 1925 *Cérémonies des douze mois: fêtes annuelles cambodgiennes*, Phnom Penh.
- Commission de Musique
 1969 *Musique Khmère*, Phnom Penh, Université Royale des Beaux Arts.
- de Martino, Ernesto
 2006 [1961] *The Land of Remorse*, London, Free Associations Books.

- Ebihara, May
 1968 *Svay. A Khmer Village in Cambodia*, Ph.D. dissertation, Columbia University.
- Giuriati, Giovanni
 1988 *Khmer Traditional Music in Washington D.C.*, Ph.D. diss., University of Maryland.
 1995 “Pambhlai: The Art of Improvisation in Khmer Traditional Music”, *Cahiers d'études franco-cambodgienne*, V: 24-54.
- Guelden, Marlane
 2007 *Thailand: Spirits among us*, Singapore, Marshall Cavendish Editions.
- Hood, Mantle
 1975 “Improvisation in the Stratified Ensemble of Southeast Asia”, *Selected Reports in Ethnomusicology*, II/2: 25-33.
- Huffman, Franklin E.
 1970 *Modern Spoken Cambodian*, New Haven, Yale University Press.
- Jankowsky, Richard C.
 2010 *Stambeli: Music, Trance, and Alterity in Tunisia*, Chicago, University of Chicago Press.
- Kapferer, Bruce.
 1991 *A Celebration of Demons: Exorcism and the Aesthetics of Healing in Sri Lanka*, Providence, Rhode Island.
- McKinley, Kathy
 2002 *Ritual, Performativity and Music: Cambodian Wedding Music in Phnom Penh*, Ph.D. diss., Brown University.
- Mills, Simon
 2003 *The Ritual Music of South Korea's East Coast Shamans: Inheritance, Training and Performance*, Ph.D. diss., University of London.
 2007 *Healing Rhythms: the World of South Korea's East Coast Hereditary Shamans*, Aldershot, Ashgate.
- Norton, Barley Mark Peter
 2000 *Music and Possession in Vietnam*, Ph.D. diss., London, University of London.
 2009 *Songs for the Spirits: Music and Mediums in Modern Vietnam*, Urbana, University of Illinois Press.
- Ovesen, Jan, and Ing-Britt Trankell
 2010 *Cambodians and Their Doctors: a Medical Anthropology of Colonial and Postcolonial Cambodia*, Copenhagen, NIAS.
- Parichat, Jungwiwattanaporn
 2006 “In Contact with the Dead: Nora Rong Khru Chao Ban Ritual of Thailand”, *Asian Theatre Journal*, XXIII/2: 374-395.
- Porée-Maspero, Eveline
 1958 *Cérémonies privées des cambodgiens*, Phnom Penh, Institut Bouddhique Éditions.
- Qureshi, Regula
 2007 [1986] *Sufi Music of India and Pakistan: Sound, Context and Meaning in Qawwali*, Oxford, Oxford University Press.

Rouget, Gilbert

1985 [1981] *Music and Trance: A Theory of the Relations between Music and Possession*, Chicago, University of Chicago Press.

Sumarsam,

1975 "Inner Melody in Javanese Gamelan Music", *Asian Music*, VII/1: 3-13.

Shahriari, Andrew C.

2006 *Khon Muang Music and Dance Traditions of North Thailand*, Bangkok, White Lotus Press.

Sutton, R. Anderson

1993 [1982] *Variation in central Javanese Gamelan Music: Dynamics of a Steady State*, Northern Illinois University.

Witzleben, J. Lawrence

1995 *Silk and Bamboo Music in Shanghai: the Jiangnan Sizhu Instrumental Ensemble Tradition*, Kent, Kent State University Press.

